

Creating a modular storage system for large technology objects at the Australian War Memorial

Bill Lang - Question and answer session

John Ashton: One of the things involved initially was the clearance between the port wing tip and the little public gallery mushroom thing at the side, and I believe the clearance was something in the range of 300mm?

Bill Lang: I'm not too sure about that because I wasn't involved in plotting it – others were involved. But a lot of the problems were foreseen at an earlier time. A lot of the drawings we've had over a long period have caused us a lot of angst. We, in many cases, see drawings that contain none of the detail, none of the measurements – they're conceptual. They've been made for exhibition consumption and for, obviously, discussion at a higher level than we operate on. So with Bradbury Aircraft Hall, with the 1945 gallery and with this [Messerschmitt] in particular there's a lot of plotting done – usually David Gordon gets left with it – but there's a lot of plotting and checking, because the conceptual drawings don't relate the true size of the aircraft to the site. One in particular, the tail of the Spitfire - if we'd done it the way they wanted, it was going to be 500mm in the wall. So we basically iron out the problems down here – we get footprints by using just traditional methods – plumb bobs, tape measures, Dave [Gordon] does a lot of drawing.

Dave Rockwell: Can I just ask the all-up weight of all the lifting gear compared to the object, and what's the capacity of these hoists?

Bill Lang: The capacity of these hoists is 1200kgs. The all-up weights and stuff involved here are well within their range. We're currently going through - as part of the OH&S - going through recertifying all the lifting gear, and checking it all as an ongoing process. As time goes on, standards change. What was acceptable, and didn't require a loading or an engineering sign-off, now today has to have a certificate - it has to have numbers... it's got to have whatever. There's a progression that goes on all the time, and what you're asking about these...if I was to say it was 1200kgs per mast hoist, I would suggest to you that they will be upgraded with recalculation, and signed off at a higher weight. So it's an ongoing process. So I can't say to you "It's exactly 'this'" at the moment because we're actually going through the process of recertifying everything.